

Padded military garments in the Wardrobe account of Edward III (1344-1349)

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The Wardrobe Accounts of Edward III of the years 1344-1349 provide a very specific account of materials spent on a number of padded arming garments. This article summarizes the 26 items from the Wardrobe list which treat such garments separately.

1. In all, 11 different types of cloth were used, most of them silks (see the table). These fabrics came in a number of colours: white, red, blue, dark blue, golden, checkered, green, diapered, grey, flesh-coloured. Lined or reinforced cendal, *Sindon afforcum*, was used in each garment, as were the cloths of Reims and Paris – both fine linen cloths. Wilton and russet were types of woollen cloths produced in England; fustian was perhaps also a woollen cloth in the times of Edward III. As we see, the cloth of all kinds was used almost indiscriminately in the making of padded garments, but some observations can be made: (a) linen (Reims, Paris cloth) was never used as outside material. (b) The lower-class padded garments were made entirely of white fustian, on the inside and outside (N2 in the table). (c) High-class padded garments were covered with silk, and only sometimes with russet (N9, 12, 13). The particularly high class of some of the items is clear from the remark “for the King” in the original text (here omitted). (d) One doublet was made entirely of green taffeta (N10).

2. The garments are defined as jupon, doublet, aketon, or simply “garments” (*garnistura*). The distinction is far from being clear, given the fact that doublet and aketon used identical amounts and types of cloth (N14-26). The presence of buttons cannot be used to deduce the type of cloth, either – both jupons (N5) and aketons (N11) had them.

3. The padding materials included raw cotton and silk fibre. The amount of stuffing varied from 1 lb to 4 lb. Raw cotton and silk fibre were usually combined in the same garment, with the typical amounts being 2 lb of raw cotton and ½ - 1 qt of silk fibre. However, two doublets were stuffed exclusively with silk fibre (N9), and of course the simpler garments contained only cotton (N2, 12, 13).

4. Decoration included ribbons of bright-coloured cloth, bronze, silver or gilded buttons, pendants, cloth of gold thread and gold plate. However, such lavish decoration is found in only 7 items out of 26 in the list under consideration.

5. Metal plates were sometimes attached to the sleeves of the doublets (N10, possibly N24), and were considered to form their part instead of being separate pieces.

6. The relationship of these garments with other armour is sometimes explicitly stated. A doublet was made for wearing under a pair of plates (N1); apparently the two doublets (N9) formed the padding layers between which the hauberk was worn [if my translation is correct]; further cases of aketons and *garnisturae* intended for wearing under hauberk are found in N11-13.

Table 1. Fabrics, raw cotton and other materials used for the production of the arming garments of Edward III’s household in 1344-1349. Blue highlighting marks the colours of fabric which are specified; orange highlighting shows which fabric was on the outside, if clear from the text. The page numbers are in Nicholas (1846).

N.	Description, as given in the original text	Zatayn Satin (ells)	Reyns Reims (ells)	Parys Paris (ells)	Fustian (ells)	Cendal/ <i>Sindon afforcum</i> (ells)	Velvet (ells)	Wilton (ells)	<i>Taffata</i> (ells)	Russet (ells)	Camoca (ells)	<i>Samyt</i> (ells)	<i>Cotoun</i> Raw cotton (lb)	Silk fibre/ <i>serico</i>	other	page
1	One doublet of satin, for King’s plates	5 ells	4 ells	4 ells									1 lb	1 quarter		p. 34
2	100 garments of white fustian, ... quilted and stuffed with cotton				920								260 lb		30 lb white thread	p. 33
3	One garment of white fustian ... stuffed with cendal and other stuffing materials		4 ells	4 ells	6 ells	1 piece (<i>pecia</i>)							1 lb	2 lb		p. 35
4	One stuffed arming jupon of red and dark blue (<i>ynde</i>) velvet with the King’s quartered arms		3 ells	3 ells		1 piece <i>syndon</i>	3 ells							1 lb	2 lb gold plate; 1 lb gold in cypress cloth; 2 pieces of large golden ribbon	p. 35

5	A jupon of blue satin powdered with blue garters, with buckles and pendants	3 ells	3 ells			½ piece		2 ells	4 ells				½ lb	¼ lb gold plate; 62 silver buttons (<i>boucles</i>); 62 silver pendants (<i>pendaunts</i>)	p. 35	
6	One doublet of checkered (<i>staccato</i>) silk		3 ells					3 ells					2 lb	1 quarter	p. 44	
7	One doublet of white linen fabric, having about the cuffs and edges a green border, worked with clouds and vines of gold and ith the motto of the King – “it is as it is”		12 short ells	30 short ells		2 ells							½ lb	1 ounce of soldered gold (<i>sondatum</i>); 1 lb gold in cypress cloth; 1 ell of green cloth for the border; 6 pieces of golden ribbon	p. 44	
8	Two doublets of green cloth, decorated with ribbons, stuffed, and with the cloth of Reims and Paris and cotton		12 ells	12 ells		2 ells							3 lb	1 quarter	2.5 ells of green (bright?) cloth for the border; 3 pieces of golden ribbon	p. 44
9	Two doublets having russet cloth on the outside, stuffed with silk, with cloth of Reims and Paris, cotton and between those two doublets the King’s hauberk		12 ells	12 ells		2 ells			5,5 ells				8 lb silk fibre 0.5 lb silk thread /yarn	2.5 pieces of loose woven cloth (<i>bultel</i>); 4 pieces of cloth of Valencia; 3 pieces of golden ribbon; 5.5 long	p. 45	

	is attached														pieces of russet	
10	One doublet covered with green taffeta, with iron plates on the sleeves having gilded rivets					1 ell			12 ells				1.5 lb	¼ lb	½ piece of <i>carde</i> (linen cloth); 3 pieces of golden ribbon	p. 45
11	9 aketons covered with bright fustian for wearing with a hauberk, stuffed, with cloth of Reims and Paris, with bultel and cotton	8 ells	58 short ells	32 ells	2 ells & 1 piece								21 lb	1.2 lb & 1 quarter	29 pieces of bultel; 4 lb of thread; 216 bronze buttons 1 piece of large golden ribbon;	p. 45
12	9 garments covered with russet, to be worn under hauberk, stuffed, with cloth of Reims, bultel, and cotton	44 short ells							22,5 ells				28 lb		9 hauberks 9 pieces of bultel	p. 46
13	Two garments covered with russet to be worn under hauberk, stuffed		12 ells						5 ells				4 lb		2 hauberks; 4 pieces of bultel	p. 46
14	One doublet of camoca	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells			2 lb	½ quarter		p. 47
15	One aketon of camoca	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells			3 lb	1 quarter		p. 47
16	One doublet of blue samit	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell						4 ells		1 lb	½ quarter		p. 47
17	One aketon covered with camoca	5 short ells	4		1 ell					5 ells			2 lb	½ quarter		p. 47
18	One aketon of diapered	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells			2 lb	1 quarter		p. 47

	camoca															
19	One doublet covered with satin	4 ells	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell							1 lb	1 quarter		p. 48
20	One aketon covered with camoca		4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells		2 lb	1 quarter		p. 48
21	One aketon covered with dark blue (ynde) camoca		4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells		1 lb	1 quarter		p. 48
22	One aketon of grey (cendryn) camoca		4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells		2 lb	1 quarter		p. 48
23	One aketon covered with flesh-coloured camoca		4 ells	4 ells		1 ell					4 ells		2 lb	1 quarter		p. 48
24	One doublet of satin with sleeves riveted with gilded rivets (i.e. with steel plates on cuffs/sleeves?)	5 ells	5 ells	5 ells		1 ell							2 lb	1 quarter		p. 49
25	One doublet covered with golden fabric (cygaston)		5 ells	5 ells		1 ell							2 lb	1 quarter	1 golden cloth (cygaston)	p. 49
26	One aketon of blue satin	4 ells	4 ells	4 ells		1 ell							2 lb	½ quarter		p. 49

Glossary

Sindon: 1a(n.) Textile; a fine linen material; also (quotations 1336-7 and 1346), used of a kind of silk, otherwise called sendal (q.v.) or cendal. Lisa Monnas notes that 'Sindons were woven both from silk and from linen during the Middle Ages, and it has been suggested that in the Great Wardrobe accounts the term denoted linen cloths [Newton, S.M. (1980), 135]. In the purchase lists, however, it seems that sindon was being substituted for cendal, a lightweight silk cloth; and in one separate account of liveries dating from the mid-

fourteenth century, the two terms are definitely interchanged' [she cites transcriptions by Nichols, N. H. (1846), pp. 12, 16, 17].(ante 1100 - circa 1337)

Ynde = dark blue

Afforcum = *aforcer* - Manufacture; to strengthen, to reinforce, appearing as a past participle meaning reinforced (cloth), lined, backed. Related senses are attested with variants of ME afforcen, MdE afforce, enforce, etc., but none dealing specifically with cloth and clothing.(circa 1240 - ante 1400 ?)

Glauco (*glaucus*) - colour term; a dark colour, silvery-grey, greyish-blue, green or blue, but by the fourteenth century used in England for yellow (silk or wool), Monnas, L. (forthcoming 2014).(circa 800 - circa 1000)

Glauco (*glaucus*) - Textile; greyish-yellow colour (but perhaps yellow or orange - cf. AND2); also by extension, a fabric of this colour. Staniland (1986) demonstrates that panni glaucus must mean yellow cloth in the context of making the leopards on the coat of arms on Edward III's jousting tunic (1345-9).(circa 1300 - 1440)

Staccato -> *scaccare scaccare*, ~iare [scacca+-are] 1 to mark like a chess-board, to decorate with squares of two different colours, (also p. ppl. as adj.) checkered.

Bultel - Accessory; loose woven cloth, or a garment made from such cloth.(ante 1400 - circa 1450)

Camoca - rich fabric, most often silk, similar to or resembling damask; associated in particular with an Italian silk cloth popular in England in the fourteenth century. Cf. Mayo, J. (1984). Lisa Monas suggest that the term applied to different types of silks at different times and places (as with many textile terms): she suggests it was used for lampas silks with a tabby ground in late 14th-century English texts, but was used for a satin-ground textile produced in Genoa from the early 15th century [Monnas, L. (1989), 286]. Italian camaca seems to have been a tabby/tabby lampas silk produced in either monochrome or polychrome (as with stripes), sometimes with figured foliage designs or with birds or animals. Patterns with vines were purchased by the English court in the early 14th century. Monnas has demonstrated that Italian camacas were produced in both 'light' and 'heavy' versions, the heavy often brocaded in gold and silver thread. The 'lighter' material seems to have been used for soft furnishings appearing in accounts of the early 14th century [Monnas, L. (1993)], and there are references to clerical vestments and secular garments of camaca from across the 14th and

Cendryn – dray fabric (colour)

Incarncion – flesh-coloured

Cygaston - Textile; cloth of gold, perhaps associated with ciclatoun (or a variant).(circa 1349)

Reyns - Textile; of Reims; cloth of Reims; fine linen cloth manufactured in or associated with Reims (Champagne region), used in particular for bedding, curtains, towels, altar furnishings, etc. At least from the 19th century, the fabric was (erroneously) attributed to the town-name Rennes in Brittany, which also produced linen in the medieval period.(ante 1275 - circa 1800)

References

Nicholas Harris Nicolas (1846). I. Observations on the Institution of the Most Noble Order of the Garter. By Sir Nicholas Harris Nicolas, G.C.M.G., addressed to Hudson Gurney, Esq., F.R.S., VicePresident; illustrated by the Accounts of the Great Wardrobe of King Edward the Third, from the 29th of September 1344 to the 1st of August 1345; and again from the 21st of December 1345 to the 31st of January 1349. *Archaeologia*, 31, pp 1163 doi:10.1017/S0261340900012273

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